

PROJECT ACRONYM: EVERSE

Grant Agreement Number:101129744

Project full title: European Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence

Call identifier: HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01

Milestone 8 (Extended Version): First evaluation of the tools and services in the form of a workshop against WP2 initial best practices (MS4) and recommendations to adapt these tools if necessary.

Version: 1.1
 Status: Final
 Dissemination Level: Public
 Means of verification: Workshop
 Due date of milestone: 30.04.2025
 Actual submission date: 29.04.2025
 Work Package: 3
 Lead partner for this deliverable: UEDIN
 Partner(s) contributing: CERTH, NLeScience Center, LAPP, UPM

Main author(s):

Name:	Elena Breitmoser
-------	---------------------

Other author(s):

Kirsty Pringle, Thomas Vuillaume, Faruk Diblen	

Introduction

The online workshop “Evaluation of tools and services to improve the quality of research software” took place on Monday 10th February from 10 CET till 16 CET.

The goals of the workshop were to provide a platform for knowledge exchange and to foster discussion about relevant tools and services used to access and improve the quality of research software, including FAIRness. We wanted to capture existing practices across communities, offer a space where participants can learn from each other and identify gaps in available tooling.

Over 90 people registered their interest in the workshop in advance, with roughly over 40 attending on the day at its peak.

The organising committee consisted of:

- CERTH: Fotis Psomopoulos
- NL eScience Center: Faruk Diblen
- LAPP/CNRS: Azza Gamgami, Thomas Vuillaume
- UEDIN (lead): Elena Breitmoser, Kirsty Pringle, Neil Chue Hong
- UPM: Daniel Garijo

Implementation

The workshop started with two sessions to introduce the wider background and allow the attendees to familiarise themselves with the EVERSE project in general, and the aims of Work Package 3 in particular. This was followed by a poll on people's backgrounds, interests and experience with software quality tools. We had three invited talks from Research Software Engineers, Mike Jackson from EPCC, and Steve Crouch and Philly Broadbent from SSI Southampton, who presented their favourite software quality tools in five-minute lightning talks to give examples of what software tools are used by experts in the field and why. This was followed by more interactive sessions with guided discussions in breakout sessions. The workshop ended with a wrap-up and reporting back from the various breakout sessions, giving the audience the opportunity to share with everyone what they had found most interesting or useful during the day.

The [indico invite](#) provides a short summary of the workshop goals, connection details and a link to the agenda and slides presented on the day.

Links to other EVERSE activities

The design and activities in the workshop drew from work completed by other EVERSE WPs.

To inform the discussions we considered the [initial best practices from the MS4 survey](#).

Their quality aspects for five out of the six research software quality dimensions (see [EVERSE RSQkit Reference Framework](#)) ‘usability’, ‘testing’, ‘documentation’, ‘performance’ and ‘security’ were used for breakout session 2 (see [spreadsheet](#)). The quality aspects were slightly re-phrased to improve clarity. The sixth research software quality dimension ‘functionality’ was not covered in the workshop because no quality aspects had been identified in the MS4 survey and only a total of three tools had been identified as linked to this quality dimension. Further investigation for the reasons might be of interest.

The tools were chosen from the [list of tools gathered for D3.1](#) according to the quality dimensions assigned to them. To keep the exercise do-able within the given timeframe we concentrated on about ten tools for each research software quality dimension.

We chose not to introduce the technical term of ‘software quality indicators’, as for example used for the Biohakathon (see <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1LLEsB7QZF32DeljFIDvCA70bvgG5QhsAZ9gZ6mCfLc/edit?usp=sharing>) to avoid confusion for non-EVERSE participants by introducing further technical terms. In addition, we did not adhere to the Biohakathon’s 17 super groups, which they equal to ‘software quality dimensions’.

Outcomes

All of the outcomes are obtained through interaction with the attendees, i.e., from a slido poll, breakout rooms with interactive discussions and parallel sessions on a variety of topics.

Slido poll session

The slido statistics showed that 40 out of 48 attendees voted in the slido poll. This number corresponds to all participants minus the eight organising committee members. The figures with the results show the actual number of voters for each of the questions asked.

As shown in Figure 1, the workshop participants came from a variety of countries across Europe.

Figure 1: City/Country workshop attendees are from.

Most of our workshop participants consider themselves to be either mid-career (38%) or established (35%), only 24% had their first employment or were still in higher education (3%), see **Error! Reference source not found.**

slido

Figure 2: Participants' career stage.

The majority of participants (56%) were not a member of one of the five EOSC Science Clusters of which Life Sciences (14%) and Astronomy & Particle Physics (11%) were most strongly represented and Social Sciences & Humanities least (3%) as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**

slido

Figure 3: Are participants a member of one of the five EOSC Science Clusters.

Nearly half (45%) use software quality tools to assess or improve their software on a weekly basis. Most other users do so daily (19%), monthly (10%) or only a few times a year (10%) and 16% never do so (see **Error! Reference source not found.**).

slido

Figure 4: How often do participants use software quality tools to assess their software.

Among the tools, which users have taken up using recently to improve the quality of their software, ‘Github repository’ (including related tools like ‘Github actions’, ‘git copilot’, ‘gitlab’) and ‘chatGPT’ are the most popular, followed by FAIR assessment tools like ‘somef’ and ‘howfairis’ and metadata tools like ‘codemeta’ and ‘CFF’ (see **Error! Reference source not found.**). The biggest challenges when adopting new software quality tools seem to be quite diverse with the main issue being documentation (see **Error! Reference source not found.**).

 Name a tool you have recently started using for software quality
 Wordcloud Poll 21 participants

slido

Figure 5: Tools participants have recently started using to assess software quality

 What is the biggest challenge you face when adopting new software quality tools?
 Wordcloud Poll 23 participants

slido

Figure 6: Biggest challenges when adopting new software quality tools.

When asked to rank on a scale from one to five how challenging users find it to address the following software quality dimensions in their work, ‘usability’ was found most challenging, followed by ‘functionality’, ‘technical performance’ and ‘documentation/technical support’, with ‘testing’ coming out as least challenging (see **Error! Reference source not found.**).

 Rank how challenging it is to address these software quality dimension in your work?

Ranking Poll 25 participants

slido

Figure 7: How challenging do participants find it to address the listed software quality dimensions.

Whereas users considered ‘functionality’ most important for their project (38%), followed by both ‘usability (23%) and ‘documentation/technical support’ (23%). ‘Technical performance’ and ‘testing’ were both ranked rather low with 8%, respectively, and no one considering ‘security’ to be important, which is quite an interesting result that so few users are interested in testing their code or optimising its performance (see **Error! Reference source not found.**).

Figure 8: Importance of software quality dimensions for participants' projects.

When asked about their favourite software tool and explain the reason for their choice, though the reasons were often not provided, the following answers were given:

- Github/gitlab was listed by several participants.
 - CI:
 - Nice integration with development workflow
 - It helps to apply all tools automatically without local setup
 - Consistent checks across the whole team
 - Github Actions
- AI tools
 - chatGPT
 - Can fix your errors
 - Claude
 - Cursor.ai
 - Blackbox.ai
 - Warp – AI gives me suggestions
- OpenSSF checklist for self-assessment
- Documentation
 - Docusaurus is very nice for documentation
 - Jupyter Notebooks
- Grep – literally searching for the culprits ('I am old school')
- Linter – for direct feedback of how to improve the code Test-Frameworks to ensure correctness and make coder more confident it really works
 - Linter
 - Formatter
- Sonarqube/sonacloud provide an extensive analysis of code quality, code smells, etc.
- Reuse.software – since checking for licences in hindsight never gets done

One participant did not answer the question but asked us to explain more about what we mean by ‘software quality tools’.

When asked which software quality dimensions from our list they feel are most undervalued and why, the following results were obtained:

- Maintainability (2x)
 - as defined by ISO/EC25010
- Usability (6x)
 - It is hard to see the result with a fresh pair of eyes (as a user would)
 - Since Research Software done for paper evaluations often is made for the paper
 - We are missing different perspectives
 - User interface design
- Security/Safety(6x)
 - Often an afterthought in Research Software
 - Sometimes seen as an add-on – ‘to be done if it works’
 - Privacy
- Resilience (2x)
 - Research Software especially at prototype level is not properly tested.
 - Reliability and robustness
- Support quality
 - Hard to measure
- Documentation (3x)
 - Time-consuming
 - Low priority for a lot of people
- Performance

Breakout Sessions

The main workshop outcomes are from breakout session 2, which consisted of five group discussions. Each group focused for 50 minutes on one of the six quality dimensions for research software as defined in the EVERSE RSQkit Reference Framework (the only dimension not discussed was ‘functionality’ because no quality aspects had been identified for this dimension previously, and only a small number of tools exist for this dimension).

The description of the task can be found in our [public github](#). The sheet for each software quality dimension was filled in to various degrees by each of the five breakout groups, the results of which can be found in the [spreadsheet](#) used.

Usability group

In the group on “Usability” one participant raised the issue that none of the measures (what we call 'best practices') we list for e.g. ‘usability’ are according to the ISO standards (see <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/iso-iec-9126-in-software-engineering/>). It started a discussion of why we re-invent the wheel, while ‘usability’ has already been established as a standard. We might also have to be careful not to overload known terms, like ‘usability’. The ISO standard was also discussed in D3.1 as well as the need to align and agree upon our groupings and definitions at the General Assembly in March 2025 in Barcelona.

Another participant pointed to one of his recent publications on [“Good modelling software practices”](#), where one of the conclusions was that “Good Modelling Software Practice means that you do not have to do it all at once. The supporting tools are numerous, and most follow a philosophy to do one thing only and to do it well: they can be learned and employed one by one. Publish your modelling software — it is good enough (Allen, 2019, Barnes, 2010)! By learning and applying one tool at a time, everyone can acquire a corpus of practices that eventually lead to better modelling software — and better research (Katz et al., 2019).“

In addition to the tools we provided originally for “Usability”, another 23 tools were added during the session.

Issues, repeatedly encountered and recommendations given to other users are:

- Restricted time available to be able to find and assess usefulness of tool
- Rather complicated for beginners to navigate their way around finding suitable tools
- Many tools are rather complex
- Some tools are poorly documented, as well as some documentation being scarily extensive
- Learn about tool usage by copying from others
- Search within your community
- Use AI to answer questions
- Watch videos about tools

Often, non-native-English speakers prefer to use tools with documentation in their native language. There is the additional challenge to ensure that translations are precise and consistent and don’t obscure what the tool is meant to help with.

Documentation group

The group focusing on the research software quality dimension of “Documentation” identified a fairly long list of tools that could help users (22 were provided by EVERSE and a further 3 were suggested by workshop participants). Overall discussion focused on the fact that while the tools were helpful, many relied on significant user input to add all the text, which is then pulled together by the tool. They highlighted the usefulness of tools that help to version control documentation and provide a DOI. None of the tools were able to automatically create user examples, though some did host examples once written. Overall, there were more tools that improve documentation, with only a couple giving some measurement of documentation

Security/Safety group

The group focusing on the research software quality dimension of “Security” only had one participant.

Parallel Sessions

We offered three 45-minute, parallel session on the topics “TechRadar”, “Missing Tools” and “Personas”.

TechRadar

In this session there were 16 attendees. At the beginning, a survey to get feedback on what are the needs and what people would like as a TechRadar was done.

The first out of a total of two questions was “What metadata on the tools and services should we collect?”

A total of 16 attendees answered. We gathered similar answers together and provide the result below.

Category	Votes
URL / Website / Link to code / Location of source code	5
Available doc, usage and use cases	4
Licence	3
Version	3
Author	3
Last Commit / Last Update / Last updated (maintained)	3
Tool direct applications / Functions / Purpose	3
Programming language supported / Programming language / Language used	3
Citation	3
Community or Domain (Who uses it)	3
Maturity, Deprecated or Future support	3
Name and Description	3
Verification and Validation	2
FAIR aspects	1
Community	1
Testing Information	1
Working easy with ... (Git, VSCode, etc.)	1
Number of users	1
Issue tracker	1
DOI	1
Extension	1
Dependencies	1
Type of software	1
Software quality indicator related to	1
Price	1

From these answers and votes, we can see what the most important metadata for the TechRadar users are. Besides basic information such as name, description and URL to the tool, users give a lot of importance to some measurement of its maturity (maturity, last commit...) and community support (community, number of users...).

The second survey question was “What metadata should be used to categorize and search for tools and services in a dashboard?”

A total of 13 attendees answered.

Category	Votes
Cores features, usage, function or field of application (linter, testing, etc.)	7
Programming language supported / Targeted programming language	4
Has docs / training material / examples	4
Rating / Rating by users?	3
License	2
Quality indicator / Quality dimension	2
Keywords / Community (e.g., oceanography) or keywords from the community	2
Date of the last update / Last commit	2
Platform: operating system/Docker/web / Platform	2
Community	2
Programming language agnostic	1
Package system	1
Type or practice is related to (basic, medium, advanced)	1
Case-uses	1
Alternatives to	1
Supported metadata standards	1
Description	1
Name	1
Availability	1

A conclusion drawn from the answers to the second survey question was that to categorize and search for software efficiently, a dashboard should focus on:

- Functionality: grouping tools by usage and purpose to match user use-cases
- Technical compatibility to filter relevant tools (programming language support, platform...)
- Trust and maintenance to assess reliability (Rating, Community...)

The third question was what the dashboard should ideally look like. The answers fall into the following three categories:

1. Tool Discovery and Exploration
 - a. a banner at the top with tool suggestions categorized by widely used by the community, release date, or new features.
 - b. or sortable table
 - c. an expandable tree or visual representation to support tool exploration.

- d. an *"alternative to"* section
 - i. note: this can be very difficult and requires lot of maintenance.
Moreover, some tools are alternatives only for a specific task but can also have other functions. Hopefully, with the right metadata and enough granularity, alternatives to the same task should appear close to each other or in the same categories in the TechRadar.
2. Search and Filtering
 - a. Flexible Filters: Support dependent or independent filters, with multiple result types (e.g., close matches).
 - b. Multiple Top-Level Categories: Allow filtering based on language targeted and functions.
 - c. Fuzzy Search Bar.
 - d. Advanced Search with Multiple Criteria: Enable search using conditions like License = "" AND Programming Language = "Python".
 - e. Refinement Levels in Search: Implement progressive detail refinement for searches.
3. User Experience and Interaction
 - a. Persona & Tier-Based Guidance: Users select who they are and what type of software they have, and the system suggests relevant indicators and resources.
 - b. Interactive Dashboard with Chatbot: Enable an AI-powered chatbot for tool discovery and assistance.

We concluded that what users need is guidance and recommendation on tools! And there are too many and not enough time to explore them all. Hence, EVERSE should make opiniated recommendations. Users expect a structured, searchable, and interactive dashboard that helps them:

- Find tools based on function, compatibility, and use case.
- Assess tool reliability through metadata on community adoption, quality, and maintenance.
- Explore and discover new tools.
- Interact dynamically through advanced filters, rankings, and AI-assisted recommendations.

Missing Tools

EVERSE has compiled a list containing 76 tools to enhance software quality; this session aimed to identify tools missing from the list and also to identify non-existent tools that would be beneficial.

The group highlighted that creating documentation for software is very important, but that there isn't a single overarching tool to create documentation, this is partly because many different types of documentation are needed (e.g. technical guides to funder reports), but even if one focuses on a single type of documentation there is a lack of tools that can help. In terms of non-existent tools, participants said that an automated documentation debugger that identifies assumed knowledge gaps would be useful. The group also discussed translation barriers for

non-English speakers, which remain a challenge as current translation technologies can introduce errors. Participants also highlighted the need for a readability checker that evaluates jargon complexity and reading levels for different audiences.

It was noted that workflow managers aren't included on the WP3 list of tools; selecting the right one is difficult, and a guidance tool akin to "Choose a License" for workflow selection could be beneficial. Relevant resources include [Kepler](#) (scientific workflow manager), [WorkflowHub](#) (workflow registry), [Nextflow](#), [Snakemake](#), and [Galaxy](#). A useful paper on workflow advantages is available [here](#).

One additional gap in tooling noted was the absence of a drag-and-drop tool for containerisation with Docker or Singularity, which would make it easier to manage dependencies and software environments. They noted that dependency tracking is well-covered by existing tools, but security analysis remains complex and fragmented.

Looking ahead to future tools, tools that assess energy efficiency and suggest optimisations would be useful, as well as solutions that streamline test generation. Verification, Validation, and Uncertainty Quantification (VVUQ) methods are essential for large-scale simulations, but comprehensive, automated tools for this purpose are scarce.

Finally, the group noted that one major recurring issue for the adoption of tools is the learning curve associated with existing tools—many useful solutions exist but are underutilised due to time constraints and lack of awareness.

Personas

In the personas session, there were four attendees, three of whom were EVERSE members. Despite the small group and limited time, excellent progress was made, and the group developed some promising personas that will help shape the EVERSE pipelines.

Participant Feedback

After the workshop we asked all participants for their feedback. We received three replies to the following questions:

1. Usefulness of the workshop
 - a. One strongly agreed
 - b. One agreed
 - c. One strongly disagreed
2. What did you learn that you will be passing on to others?
 - a. "The AI/ML/LLM are not as popular as I had thought"
 - b. "That EVERSE do not understand basic software engineering principles related to design and software quality. Tools do not improve software quality"
3. Do you have any comments about the event organisation? What worked and what didn't work?
 - a. "Script the handovers"
 - b. What didn't work: The idea that you can map software development tools such IDEs (VS Code), version control (Git), build tools (CMAKE) etc and equate "
4. Do you have any other comments you'd like to provide?
 - a. "The live polls were engaging and interesting: more please."
 - b. "van Vliet (2008) Software Engineering: Principles and Practice should be core reading"

What to pass on to other EVERSE WPs

The outcomes of this workshop can feed back into

- T3.2: How to integrate and consolidate the tools
- T3.3: The dashboard
- T5.3: The monthly series on tools and best practices to increase software quality
- The list of tools from D3.1
- The Reference Framework
- The overall discussion on the alignment issues across EVERSE

Conclusions

The workshop and its high attendance confirm a strong interest in tools and services to improve the quality of research software in the wider research software community. We identified several re-occurring themes. Users would like guidance and recommendations on tools, and EVERSE could support this need, even with opinionated recommendations.

Time and steep learning curves are an issue for many users regarding uptake of a new tool, particularly when tools are complex and either extensively documented or not well documented at all. Another issue is (not) offering tools in languages beyond English as well as the challenge to avoid mistranslations.

There were several recommendations on what the future dashboard should focus on.

Both the preparation of the workshop and running breakout session 2, illuminated the need to align definitions and dimensions across EVERSE, including the need to not neglect already existing definitions and standards.

EVERSE might want to understand why the software quality dimension “functionality” appears to be underrepresented compared to the five other ones, whereas “security” appeared to be of least importance and interest to the users, both visible from the poll and the lack of attendance of the breakout session dedicated to “security/safety”. We think there is a rather large gap between recognition of importance and interest. Often people have very little knowledge about security and do not know how and where to start. Tools that are very easy to use and make recommendations, rather than simply give a score, for improvement are essential.